

COMPOUND WORDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article discusses Uzbek and English compound words, their comments on the formation, calcification, semantic features.

Keywords: English, Uzbek, component, syntactic, phrase, compound word, morpheme.

INTRODUCTION

In English and Uzbek, compound words are orthographically similar. In this respect, they are divided into three types: compound words, hyphenated, separated. In both languages, compound words have different aspects from word combinations. The difference between a compound word and a compound word is that the components of a compound word are morphemes, and the components of a compound word are words. Therefore, the components of a compound word as a whole have the same lexical meaning and there is no syntactic connection between the components. This means that the elements of the phrase retain their independence and are in a free state. There is a syntactic relationship. The elements of a compound word have a single meaning, are interconnected and have a lexical relationship. Compound words in English and Uzbek languages are divided into the following types according to their semantic features¹:

- a) fully justified;
- b) partially based;
- c) unfounded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the categories of speech, compound words are classified as follows: a) in terms of function; b) the content of compound words in terms of connection; c) in terms of different ways of joining.

In terms of connecting the components of compound words, the compatibility of the components, the adaptation and connection of the possessive and the participle are also of special importance.

In the classification of compound words, their types are known and popular due to their semantic properties. According to their semantic properties, compound words are divided into the following types.

¹ Madaliev B. Compound words in modern Uzbek language // Uzbek language and literature. - T., 2016. - P. 104.37.

- a) fully justified;
- b) partially based;
- d) unfounded.

Unfounded compound words. At the same time we do not find any connection between the original meaning and structure of independent morphemes. As a result, the lexical meaning cannot be inferred from the bases. For example: fiddlesticks - "nonsense rubbish" - to be "bekorchi yoki norozi". Fiddle - fraud, stick - basically means to stick. Neither of the two independent grounds means "bekorchi yoki norozi bo`lish" and they are therefore unfounded. Night - cap - "a drink taken before going to bed at night" - "tunda uxlashdan oldin ichiladigan dori", sweet - tooth - one who likes sweet food and drink - "shirin ovqat yoki ichimliklarni yaxshi ko`rmoq"².

We can see from all the examples that such a meaning cannot be understood from the lexical meaning of the compound word. The meaning of some of the compound words in this group in the whole word or in the components is logically related to the original meaning of the word. The above example of sweet-tooth is an example of this: sweet - sweet, tooth - tooth, and the word sweet in the whole word is logically connected with the meaning of liking a sweet drink or food. In general, there are examples that do not have a semantic status, for example, dog-days - "the hottest part of July and August" - "iyul va avgust oylaridagi eng issiq payt". a person who complains, cold-blooded - a person whose speech is unpleasant.

A large number of compound words in modern English are made up of nouns and adjectives. For example, arm - chair, baby - sitter, boiling - point, knee - high, rain - driven. Ravish and its conjunctions are also important: indoors, within, outside, however, we cannot call such compound words made with ravish productive.

1) the structure of compound words is only a certain state of a place make a compound word by identifying: door - handle, rain - driven. This method is the most effective word formation in modern English. In the Uzbek language: koksulton, iskabtopar, homkalla.

2) The structure of compound words with connecting elements: Fro - Asian Sino-Japanese on the speedometer, Anglo Saxon, electro-dynamic on the tragicomic, handicraft, handiwork. Sometimes consonant sounds can also help

² Mamatov N. On the relationship between compound words and simple words // Uzbek language and literature. - T., 2012. - № 2. - P. 7-12.

the connecting element, for example: sportsman, tradesman, saleswoman, bridesmaid, statesman, landsman³.

3) make compound words in terms of different ways of joining.

In Uzbek, compound words are additionally divided into:

1) compatibility of ingredients: wedding, book-loving, worldview.

2) as a result of adaptation and connection of the owner and the cut:

The bride, the bridesmaids, the bridesmaids (ceremonies).

According to the structure and spiritual classification, the types of endocentric and exocentric compound words are a matter of some consideration. Endocentric (endo-within) compound words - such compound words consist of two independent morphemes and give a new meaning. But the difference is that the components have to define each other. In endocentric compound words, the head word is the determinant, and the subordinate word is the determinant. Usually these are made in two different ways. The 1st subordinate word comes before the dominant word and the 2nd subordinate word is the first word in the compound word component. Usually the subordinate component clarifies and concretizes the meaning of the main element that came before or after it. At the same time, attention is focused on the main part.

In both languages being compared, this phenomenon is more common in compound nouns. For example: back door - "orqa eshik", front door - "asosiy kirish eshigi". Door is defined, back and front are its determinants and determine exactly what the door is.

CONCLUSION

In modern English and Uzbek, compound words are an effective way to enrich the vocabulary, and each branch of linguistics studies this phenomenon from its own point of view. Although compound words have been studied in the past in scientific research, they have not lost their relevance. Because new words always come into the language. The old ones can lose their status over time.

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